

OPTICAL EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL STUDY ON COMPRESSION BUCKLING BEHAVIORS OF COMPOSITE PANEL STIFFENED BY I-TYPE RIBS

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ABSTRACT

During the buckling of the composite structure, the local damages, such as fiber breakages and matrix cracks, occur at microscale, and then gradually propagate into the micro-domain damages of delamination with the increase of buckling deflections and the conversion of buckling modes. A combination of methods of strategy which combines optical measurements and numerical calculations was developed to study the buckling behavior and failure modes of composite panel with I-type ribs under compression. Utilizing the non-contact optical means for non-destructive testing, the full-field buckling deflections/evolution and compressive failure of the panel surface were systematically collected for mechanical analysis. Based on continuum mechanics modeling, the buckling and post-buckling behaviors of the composite panel were predicted and compared with the buckling shapes that were obtained from experiments. The numerical simulation and experimental test technique in the work provides a useful tool to study the compressive buckling behaviors of stiffened composite panels.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) have excellent mechanical properties such as high strength and high stiffness. Stiffened CFRP panels are constructed with skin and stabilized by ribs, which are often used as lightweight structures with high bending stiffness and buckling resistance. The use of advanced CFRP structures with the advantage of decreasing the structural weight has wide application potential in the aerospace industry. The stiffened panel occurs local buckling and deformation under compressive loading and the buckling load is firstly supported by the skin and rib together. Then the panel enters post-buckling and continue to bear the load until the ultimate failure [1-2].

The finite element method (FEM) can be used to optimize the stiffness design of rib/ skin and accurately predict the post buckling behavior of composite structures. It is also used to improve the safety of the ultimate loading capacity and utilize the bearing potential of post-buckling. It is important to verify the correctness of the FEM prediction model with abundant experimental data [3-4]. The buckling mode and out-of-plane displacement of the panel can usually be measured by shadow Moiré method [5-6] or digital image correlation method [4, 7]. However, the shadow Moiré method is difficult to automatically extract the out-of-plane displacement, and the digital image correlation method is not suitable for the measurement of the discontinuity surface of stiffened panel.

In this paper, fringe projection profilometry (FPP) and FEM numerical analysis were utilized to study the buckling behavior of the CFRP panel stiffened by I-shape ribs under compression.. The main purpose of this paper is to the abundant experimental data to validate the FEM numerical modeling and simulation process, which are used to predict the buckling and post-buckling behavior of the stiffened CFRP panel under compression. Firstly, the basic principle of FPP for measuring the buckling process is introduced, including dynamic phase-shifting method (PS), multi-frequency phase unwrapping method (MPU) and the phase/height conversion method. Second, the compression experiment of the I-shape stiffened CFRP panel was carried out, and the loading history and strain

evolution process were given. Then, the projection fringe patterns were processed to obtain the buckling modes and deflection distributions at different moments. Finally, a FEM model was established to predict the buckling behavior of the stiffened panel. The simulation results were compared with the optical measurements to discuss the difference between them.

2 PRINCIPLE OF FPP

When a 2D fringe pattern is projected on an object surface, the fringe is modulated by the object height. So the distorted fringe pattern implies the height information. As shown in Fig. 1, the FPP system is consisted of a projector, a camera and a computer. A set of designed fringe patterns in the extended screen of the computer are projected onto the object surface by the projector, while the camera is synchronously triggered to capture the distorted fringe images, which display on the computer screen.

Figure 1: Light path of FPP system.

When a sine fringe pattern is projected onto the object surface, the distorted fringe can be expressed as

$$I = a + b \cos[2\pi f + \varphi] \quad (1)$$

where the constants a and b represent the background light and surface reflectivity, respectively. f is the spatial frequency of the fringe pattern projected onto the reference plane. φ is the fringe phase caused by the height of the corresponding object. If the object is removed, a parallel fringe on the reference plane has a corresponding light intensity as

$$I_r = a + b \cos[2\pi f + \varphi_r] \quad (2)$$

where φ_r is an initial phase of the reference plane.

The phase difference between the object and the reference plane is

$$\Delta\varphi = \varphi - \varphi_r \quad (3)$$

For a given optical path, a relationship between the phase difference and the object height is a known invariant, which can be written in the series of

$$h = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} A_k \Delta\varphi^k \quad (4)$$

The above relationship can be calibrated from the mapping data between the known height and the measured phase difference. The $k+1$ unknowns (A_0, A_1, \dots and A_k) can be determined by least squares method from a series of height data obtained from a calibrated block with known height.

Here, a PS method is used to determine the phase difference. After a shifted phase δ_n is introduced into Eq. (1), the phase shifted light intensity becomes

$$I_n = a + b \cos[2\pi f + \varphi + \delta_n] \quad (5)$$

In a four-step PS method, the phase shift is $\delta_n=0, \pi/2, \pi$ and $3\pi/2$ ($n=1, 2, 3, 4$), respectively. Four sine fringe patterns are projected onto the object surface. Phase calculation is performed on four adjacent images in a series of acquired images to obtain the wrapped phase φ^w as

$$\varphi^w = \text{wrap}[\phi] = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{I_4 - I_2}{I_1 - I_3} \right) \quad (6)$$

where the intensity images of I_1, I_2, I_3, I_4 correspond to the phase shifts of $0, \pi/2, \pi$ and $3\pi/2$, respectively. $\text{wrap}[]$ is a wrapping function and the wrapped phase φ^w has a value in the range of $[-\pi/2, \pi/2]$, which can be extended to the range of $[-\pi, \pi]$.

In practice, a phase unwrapping algorithm is used to obtain the object phase φ . For a discontinuous surface, a multi-frequency phase unwrapping (MPU) method can be used to avoid error propagation related to neighboring pixels [8]. Several sets of phase-shifted fringe patterns with different fringe frequencies are projected onto the object surface and the wrapped phase φ_i^w at the corresponding fringe frequency f_i is obtained by the four-step PS method. Thus, the unwrapped phase φ_i at the corresponding fringe frequency f_i is written as

$$\varphi_i = \varphi_i^w + \text{INT} \left(\frac{\varphi_j \cdot (f_i / f_j) - \varphi_i^w}{2\pi} \right) \cdot 2\pi \quad (7)$$

where the superscript w represents a wrap operator, and $\text{INT}()$ is the rounding function. The unwrapped phases of φ_i and φ_j correspond to the fringe frequencies of f_i and f_j , respectively. It is noted that the unwrapped phase φ_1 is equal to the wrapped phase φ_1^w when the fringe frequency is $f_1=1$; as such, no further phase unwrapping is required. As the phase accuracy for the fringe frequency f_1 is insufficient, the actual fringe frequency f_i needs to be further increased.

Figure 2: Flowchart for the multi-frequency phase-shifting method.

(a-e) Four sets of distorted fringe images with different frequencies f_i ($i = 1, 4, 16, 64$ and 128),

(f-j) the corresponding wrapped phases φ_i^w obtained by four-step PS,

(k) the unwrapped phase φ_1 equals its wrapped phase φ_1^w ,

(l) the unwrapped phase φ_4 is obtained by MPU combining (k) and (g),

(m-o) the unwrapped phases for fringe frequency of 16, 64 and 128 can be obtained similar to step (l)

In this experiment, we designed five sets of phase-shifted fringe patterns with different fringe frequencies of f_i ($i = 1, 4, 16, 64$ and 128), which were projected onto the I-shape stiffened CFRP panel in turns. The camera collected the distorted fringe images sequentially, as shown in Fig. 2(a) to Fig. 2(e). Then, the PS method in Eq. (6) was used to obtain the wrapped phase for each fringe frequency, as shown in Fig. 2(f) to Fig. 2(j). When the fringe frequency is f_1 , the unwrapping phase φ_1 (Fig. 2k) equals to its corresponding wrapped phase φ_1^w (Fig. 2f). However, when the fringe frequency is f_4 , the unwrapped phase φ_4 (Fig. 2l) is calculated by the MPU method in Eq. (7) from the combined wrapped phase φ_4^w (Fig. 2g) with the unwrapped phase φ_1 (Fig. 2k). This is similar to the next higher fringe frequency, where only the most accurate unwrapping phase φ_{128} (Fig. 2o) is required for the actual measurement.

3 EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Specimen description

As shown in Fig. 3(a), the geometry of I-shaped stiffened CFRP panel is 530 mm (length) \times 405 mm (width) \times 1.5 mm (thickness). Three I-shaped ribs are distributed equally along the longitudinal direction of the panel. The rib height is 41 mm from the skin surface and is composed of the upper edge, lower edge, and vertical strips. The dimensions of the upper edge, lower edge, and vertical strips are 24 mm (width) \times 3.38 mm (thickness), 52 mm (width) \times 1.69 mm (thickness), and a thickness of 3.38 mm, respectively. The skin was paved with automatic paving machines, then all ribs and the skin were solidified by a co-curing process. The prepared specimen is shown in Fig. 3(b).

Figure 3: (a) Geometry of the composite panel reinforced by I-shape ribs and (b) the prepared specimen

Six pairs of strain gauges were pasted back-to-back on the skin of the stiffened panel, as shown in the cross in Fig. 3 (a), and used to monitor the magnitude of surface deformation in the loading history. In addition, the two ends of the specimen were reinforced by the steel frames potting resin in order to ensure that the specimen ends does not fail early, as shown in Fig. 3(b).

3.2 Test procedure

The compressive experiment on the I-shaped stiffened CFRP panel was conducted in a self-made fixture. As shown in Fig. 4, a trapezoidal loading head, which was fixed to a four-column testing machine (CSS-100T, Changchun tester Co.), can gradually transfer the compressive load. The specimen was fixed between a pair of rigid blocks in the middle of the fixture to ensure symmetrical compression. Both laterals of the specimen were supported using bolts to simulate simply supported boundary conditions. The force sensor and the displacement sensor are used to measure the axial load and displacement during the loading process, and the strain gauges are used to record the strain gauge data.

Figure 4: Experimental setup

Furthermore, a set of multi-frequency fringe patterns were projected onto the front of the specimen using a projector (TLP-X2000 3LCD) with a projection and shooting rate of 4 fps. The resulting images from the projections were sequentially collected by a camera (Guppy F-080B) to measure the full-field deflection. The projector illuminated from the front of the specimen, and a rectangular measurement area of the specimen including the ribs and the skin was measured.

3.3 Load history and strain analysis

Fig. 5(a) shows the load-time curve. The load is shown to increase linearly with time, with a loading displacement rate of 0.2 mm/min. The maximum compression load was approximately 378 kN during the whole loading process.

Figure 5: (a) Loading history and (b) Strain curves for different positions

Fig. 5(b) describes the strain-time curves of some strain gauges. Importantly, a strain bifurcation occurs on the surface of the panel when the experiment was carried out for approximately 1 min; the strains at some locations were positive or negative. The observed strain bifurcation can be explained by the local buckling, convex and/or concave, exhibited by the stiffened panel at different locations.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Full-field deflection

As shown in Fig. 2(a-e), five sets of PS fringes were experimentally collected before loading. Real-time measurement of 3D morphology was finished by the four-step PS method and MPU technology, and the unwrapped phase φ_{128} at the highest fringe frequency was obtained, as shown in Fig. 2(o). The same procedure for the reference plane can also be obtained, and thus, the object phase is obtained by the unwrapped phase φ_{128} subtracting the reference phase. The multi-frequency fringe projection method is used to obtain the phase map at different moments. Phase variation can be obtained by

subtracting the object phase of the initial time before being transformed into the deflection as shown in Fig. 6. It can be seen that the local buckling of the panel showed an obvious deflection evolution. An increase in the load causes the local buckling to appear gradually in the skin between the ribs and the convex/concave wave which increases in intervals. It is important to note that the full-field deflection data obtained is more comprehensive for understanding the evolution of local buckling.

Figure 6: Local buckling deflection evolves with the load, “+”denotes convex and “-” means concave

Figure 7: The finite element model for stiffened composite panel, (a) boundary constraint conditions and (b) the deflection field, the convex represents by red color and the concave represents by blue color

4.2 Numerical analysis

The numerical simulation was carried out based on FEM modeling. According to the actual clamping situation of specimen, all the displacements of the nodes at both ends of specimen are restricted as fixed boundary condition, except the axial displacements of the nodes at loading end are set free. To keep the displacements of loading behaving a uniform axial deformation, the nodes at the loading end are connected together in axial direction through a rigid rod, as shown in the Fig. 7(a).

Corresponding simulations were carried out on ABAQUS software. The S8R element was applied to discretize the skin and ribs, whose interface was modeled using the cohesive COH3D8 element. The compression load in modeling was applied at one end in the displacement control mode, and a large deformation analysis was carried out based on the simulation results. The out-of-displacement of the finite element analysis under the limit load is shown in Fig. 7(b).

It can be seen that the numerical analysis can be verified by the experimental results. A careful examination of the local buckling mode reveals the following buckling behavior of the stiffened panel skin. The local buckling becomes clearer, displaying three convex and three concave peaks along the line, with an increasing load.

9 CONCLUSIONS

The digital fringe projection profilometry was used to study the compressive buckling mode of CFRP composite panel stiffened by I-shape ribs. The sinusoidal fringe patterns were projected on to the specimen surface, and the dynamic phase-shifting method and multi-frequency unwrapping technique were used to real-time monitor the buckling process of the CFRP composite panel under compression. The ultimate failure load is 378 kN and the strain bifurcation occurred on the skin surface, which indicates that the wall has local buckling. The full-field optical measurement results showed that three concaves and three convexes interval distributed on the skin between the ribs. As the load increases, the deflection on the local buckling becomes stronger until the ribs are unstable at the ultimate load. The experimental results are in good agreement with the FEM prediction, which is helpful to explore the further analysis of the failure mechanism and failure mode.

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